
EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIA: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS.

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the challenges of employee productivity in Nigeria and suggests several solutions. Employee productivity refers to the magnitude of output produced by an institution or organization's staff within a specific period or appropriate time scale. It is the continuous improvement of employees' performance that greatly impacts the prosperity, growth, and economy of a nation. For these reasons, organizational leaders in Nigeria are responsible for stimulating and fostering a culture that increases employee productivity. Training and development, security (life and property insurance), workplace ethics, salary increases, employee incentives, and promotions should be provided to ensure optimum results from employees. Also, systematic approaches for assessing employees' performance should be critically determined.

Keywords: Employee Productivity, Salary Increase, Welfare Packs, Workplace Ethics, Reward and Promotion, Training and Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is a developing country with a growing economy, and the nation's wealth can only increase through increased employee productivity. A productive workforce is the engine behind every successful business in a nation. Therefore, employees are integral to the daily operations of businesses as they contribute to overall success by adding value to their diverse job roles in various organizations within the nation (Zeb-Obipi, 2022). Productivity is crucial because it is a tool that ensures greater social and economic development and serves as a means to improve the quality and living standards of citizens. Therefore, it is a major driving force behind economic growth, with total reliance on the knowledge, innovation, wealth creation, and creativity of employees (Ekpo-Ufot, 1986). Increasing productivity is a means of enhancing the overall prosperity of the Nigerian economy as a whole. According to the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER, 2021), productivity refers to the output of a firm or industry per unit of input, including labour, capital, or materials. It is the level of output produced, usually measured as output per worker, output per hour worked, or output per unit of capital.

Employee productivity refers to the efficient utilization of manpower and time (hours) to complete important and relevant tasks that generate revenue and contribute to the achievement of an organization's goals. It is the continuous improvement of workers' performance that greatly impacts the prosperity and growth of an economy. Lawler (2003) argues that the prosperity and survival of an organization are determined by employees' strategy and how they are treated. Nigeria has a large and youthful population that can bring creativity and innovation to the workforce. The employees in Nigeria are determined people who are full of zeal and energy always to execute their job duties. However, they face challenges that lower their productivity and instigate a negative attitude towards work. According to Das and Baruah (2013), negative work attitudes can be categorized into three dimensions: mental, social, and physical. Each dimension may have a varying degree of impact on workers' attitudinal outcomes. When employees perceive or experience negative work relationships, non-supervisory or non-organizational support, unconducive work conditions, insufficient training and career development opportunities, low compensation, heavy workloads, and long working hours, it can deter them from investing time and effort into accomplishing organizational tasks. For instance, civil service workers often engage in side businesses due to complaints of insufficient salary, lack of performance-based rewards, low incentives, limited promotion opportunities, and increased work pressure. They complain that the workload is cumbersome for personnel to handle, and their monthly salary is insufficient to meet their needs. As a result, they resort to other means of surviving and living up to expectations and family demands. These behaviours result in poor work ethics and negative attitudes in the workplace. It brings about nonchalant attitude towards work, skipping important meetings, arriving late to work, being rude to co-workers or senior management staff, and a lack of initiative or responsibility-taking. Several other issues that contribute to a lack of productivity include poor work ethics, absenteeism, and job insecurity. Workers residing in the northern part of Nigeria face uncertainty, kidnapping, banditry, and the Boko Haram insurgency. With these measures, workers are restricted to working only a few hours per day (9:00 am - 2:00 pm) and a few days per week (Monday - Wednesday), which effectively reduces their overall working hours. In contrast, employees in higher grade levels are allowed to work remotely from home. However, in Zeb-Obipi's (2022) "People Management Tripod and Worker Productivity: Solute, Solvent, and Solution," it is argued that an employee's personality trait influences his work attitude. Perhaps, this explains the reason why employees who find themselves in similar job contexts exhibit different attitudes

toward the job, co-workers, and organizations. It is in consideration of the above that this paper outlines the challenges of employee productivity in Nigeria and proposes suitable solutions to address these challenges.

THEORETICAL UNDERPINNING AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This work is grounded in human capital theory, systems theory, and motivational theory. According to Noel and Finocchio (2022), human capital theory refers to the collective skills, knowledge, and intangible assets of workers that can be utilized to generate economic value in society. It is the economic value of employees' experience and skills. The theory proposes that employees can increase productivity through training and development. According to Gary (1975), employees' education and training are significant investments that contribute to productivity. They are important components that drive continuous innovation and creativity. Mason and Matas (2015) posit that skills and knowledge are essential components for employees to meet competitive demands. Therefore, organizations are responsible for building the capacity of employees. Nassazi (2013) asserts that investing in employee training and development increases their psychological capital and enhances their career advancement.

System theory, as proposed by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy (George, 2007), asserts that a system is influenced by internal factors (such as workers' inputs) and external elements (such as forces from the external environment). Therefore, it is considered an open system. The theory is concerned with assessing various forms of employees' inputs, which include skills, expertise, educational qualifications, and other useful materials that contribute to productivity. Consequently, the success of a nation greatly depends on the contribution of its employees to the organization (Zeb-Obipi, 2022). Employees' decisions, contributions, and actions are vital components that affect every sector of the nation and contribute to the success of organizations. With this, society relies on its workforce for essential inputs that contribute to productivity.

The motivation theory proposes that workers need to be motivated at every level of the organizational hierarchy in order to enhance workplace effectiveness and efficiency (Maslow, 1954). Employees are motivated by various needs, which are influenced by multiple factors that can vary from person to person and in different situations. According to Maslow, there are five basic constructs of the human hierarchy of needs, which include physiological, safety, love and belongingness, esteem, and self-actualization needs. The physiological needs entail basic requirements (such as air, food, shelter, etc.) that are necessary for maintaining employees' well-being. Safety needs refer to the need for a secure and stable environment. Employees want to experience order, predictability, and safety in their lives and properties within society. Love and belongingness needs include friendship, trust, intimacy, and acceptance. There is a need for receiving and giving love, respect, and affection in the workplace. Esteem needs, as the fourth level of the hierarchy, include self-confidence, self-worth, accomplishment, and respect. Maslow indicates that the need for respect or reputation is most important to employees. Self-actualization is the highest level of need in Maslow's hierarchy. He describes this level as the individual's desire to achieve their full potential in life. Therefore, this theory suggests that employees' behaviour is motivated by the need for overall satisfaction.

THE CONCEPT OF EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY

Various scholars from across the globe have postulated differing viewpoints on the concept of productivity. Krugman (1994) affirms that productivity is measured by the "Gross

Domestic Product (GDP) per hour worked." Robbins, as cited in Zeb-Obipi (2015: 21), mentions that productivity encompasses both the effectiveness and efficiency of a firm's human resources. Bhatti and Qureshi (2007) agree that productivity is a performance measure that encompasses both effectiveness and efficiency. Therefore, employee productivity refers to the magnitude of output produced by an employee in a specific period or within an appropriate time scale. The International Labour Organization (ILO) defines employee productivity as the efficiency with which labour is utilized in production. It is measured by the amount of output produced per unit of labour input (ILO, 2019). The Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) defines employee productivity as the measure of work completed by an employee within a specific timeframe, taking into account the resources utilized (SHRM, 2021). It is the combination of effectiveness (doing the right things) and efficiency (doing things right) in achieving the goals and objectives of an organization (Harvard Business Review, 2019). Employees are more likely to contribute to the success of an organization when they experience a great level of job satisfaction and fulfillment. According to Locke (1976), job satisfaction is defined as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state that arises from evaluating one's job or job experience." This positive state of mind in an employee is what leads to job satisfaction and enhances efficiency and effectiveness in achieving desired outcomes. Miller and Monge (1986) observed that satisfaction increases productivity by providing a conducive working environment, bringing high-quality motivation, and increasing working capabilities. Berg (1999) asserts that employees should be provided with incentives so as for them to expend discretionary effort and the means to acquire appropriate skills. Markos and Sridevi (2010) submitted that organizations should consider investing in employees' training and development as these are capable of increasing efficiency and effectiveness in the workplace. Organizations should, therefore, have a culture that encourages employee productivity.

2. CHALLENGES

Employees in Nigeria face various challenges that lower their productivity and contribute to a decline in the nation's economy. These challenges include the following:

➤ ***Insecurity:*** This is the feeling of uncertainty and inadequacy that leads to anxiety. It is the exposure to chronic threats to lives, properties, and jobs that depresses employees' confidence and has a negative impact on businesses. This, in turn, affects investment decisions. According to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA, 2021), insecurity is defined as a state of lacking safety and stability, which is frequently caused by conflict, violence, or instability in governance and social structures. It is a pervasive feeling of vulnerability and apprehension (American Psychological Association, 2021). On the contrary, security refers to the protection from hidden and harmful disruptions in the daily activities of workers. According to the UNDP Human Development Report (1994), security is the essential safeguarding of fundamental human lives in a manner that promotes human freedom and satisfaction. It encompasses protection from persistent threats, defense against abrupt and detrimental disruptions in daily routines, and can be classified into various categories such as economic security, health security, food security, environmental security, personal security, and political and community security. It is the protection of crucial aspects of human lives in a manner that would enhance human freedom and fulfillment (Commission on Human Security, 2003). However, the nation (Nigeria) has been witnessing constant and unparalleled security challenges. Workers feel insecure moving freely within the country and it lowers national productivity. Stewart (2004 p.264) revealed that "insecurity affects a nation's economy by reducing economic growth; lowering exports,

resulting from falls in production and shift towards domestic markets; lowering consumption per head; and increasing the share of government expenditure to the military thereby, lowering the share of social expenditure". Insecurity in Nigeria has cost enormous material resources and has diminished public confidence in the government. It has a great impact on human lives, properties, and well-being; therefore, the government should take responsibility and ensure security in all measures, as it is one of the fundamental human rights of the people. Section 14 (2b) of the Nigerian 1999 constitution clearly states that "the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the government".

Heightened insecurity has aroused moments of chaos in Nigeria, as kidnapping is rampant in the South-South and South-East which is the oil base of the nation, and people from all walks of life are victims. Though, it is the right of people to live in dignity and freedom from fear, with an equal opportunity to enjoy their human rights and fully develop their human potential (UN General Assembly, 2012); in the North, Banditry and Boko Haram insurgence is the order of the day. In 2009, the Borno State northern Nigeria was attacked by Boko Haram members and over 4,000 people (citizens and expatriates) were killed (Edukugho, 2012). Also, a series of deadly and costly bombing campaigns have been witnessed in the country - the bombing of the police headquarters in Abuja, the independence anniversary bombing, the bombing of the military base in Kaduna, the bombing of the United Nations office in Abuja (cited in Egbewole, 2013 & Adegbami, 2013). These have caused reputable organizations to restrict the movement of their workers from especially the northern and eastern parts of the nation. Therefore, the inability to travel freely reduces the productivity of those affected. Workers have become more risk-averse regarding the places they visit and the people they interact with.

Under the atmosphere of banditry and kidnapping, creativity, and innovation are diminished; whereas, they are the bedrock of productivity, and vital engines needed to drive change and growth in every sector of Nigeria. Security of life and property are the basic goals of any civilized nation. It is paramount for the nation's development and the absence of it can result in a loss of economic growth and development (Achumba, Ighomereho & Akpor-Robaro, 2013). According to the United Nations Development Programme (1994), security refers to the safeguarding of individuals from unforeseen and harmful disruptions in their daily work routines. Therefore, when the government is unable to solve the problem of insecurity in the nation, it shows a sign of incompetence in the administration. Security is what provides workers with the space to reflect and be creative and innovative. Adegbami (2013) states that security is synonymous with freedom from danger, fear, and doubt, among other things. It relates to the presence of peace, safety, and the protection of human and physical resources or the absence of crisis (Otto & Ukpere, 2012). When security is absent, the country loses many creative people to the Western world. Studies have shown that Nigerians in the diaspora are among the leaders in innovation and change in many sectors (Joseph, 2014; Wapmuk, Akinkuotu & Ibonye, 2014; Lampert, 2009). Research conducted by NOI polls found that "almost 88% of respondents disclosed that they are seeking work opportunities abroad." Also, "83% of doctors who filled out the survey and are based abroad are licensed in Nigeria, indicating that they completed their medical education in Nigeria and worked for a while before leaving Nigeria (IOM, 2023). Healthcare delivery in Nigeria has collapsed due to insecurity. A vivid example of this is the recent case of health workers who lost their lives while immunizing children in different parts of northern Nigeria (Adegbami, 2013). The effect was that immunization activities were put on hold as health workers stayed away for their safety. Also, insecurity has a significant negative impact on the Nigerian economy as it hampers the productivity of businesses. For instance, the manufacturing business relies

heavily on the availability and consistent supply of raw materials for production. However, insecurity has disrupted the supply of these raw materials, obstructing production activities. It also affects the marketing of finished products, as workers find it difficult to move freely in certain areas of the country. Thus, security is crucial for both productivity and national growth.

➤ **Negative Working Environment:** This is a workplace setting that has a widespread negative impact on the psychological and emotional well-being of employees. It is characterized by a range of negative experiences which include office harassment, bullying, discrimination, poor communication, low job satisfaction, low morale, and high turnover rates. According to the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM, 2021), a negative work environment is an environment in which employees feel threatened, stressed, or uncomfortable due to toxic leadership, poor communication, and lack of support from management. It is an environment in which employees are treated unfairly, have limited opportunities for growth and development, and experience high levels of stress and anxiety (Harvard Business Review, 2018). It is characterized by poor working conditions, lack of job security, and low levels of job satisfaction, which can lead to stress, burnout, and other negative consequences for employees (ILO, 2020). The working environment has long-term consequences on workers' well-being; and affects their physical health, mental health, and longevity of life. However, a negative working environment is characterized by unprofessional acts or behaviour, ineffective communication, punitive practices or policies, and strained relationships between workers and leaders of an organization. For instance, when a superior staff of an organization micromanages or undermines a junior worker; takes credit for his work performance, and speaks negatively about him, it leads to a decline in employee mental agility, work quality, and productivity. According to Amble (2005), a negative work environment can result in lower business performance and a higher level of stress experienced by workers. At different levels in an organization, workers are faced with several operational and organizational challenges where they are expected to invest time and energy; however, in a negative working environment, they refuse to invest, which ultimately creates challenges for the organization and slows down their productivity. In contrast, when a conducive work environment is provided for workers, it boosts their willingness to contribute to the overall growth of the organization.

A good working environment has a significant positive impact on employees as it improves their physical and mental health; reduces stress and promotes work-life balance; improves physical and mental health; stimulates creativity and innovation; encourages collaboration at work; and supports knowledge sharing. It also positively impacts organizational outcomes as it increases productivity, helps retain talented and experienced employees and improves customer satisfaction. According to Saha (2016), comfort in the workplace is necessary to retain quality workers, increase productivity and maintain a competitive edge. It is crucial to increase the comfort level of workers to increase profit for organizations and society at large. A conducive workplace can increase worker satisfaction, motivation, and retention. It can also influence the level of knowledge and skills of workers, and how they respond (with innovation and creativity) to business. According to Gutnick (2007), the design of the workplace is a significant driver in reducing employee stress; and a healthy work environment involves transparency, cooperation, teamwork, and accomplishment. Consequently, for any business to thrive, these must be put in place.

➤ **Bureaucracy and Red Tape:** These are the excessive formalities, rigid procedures, and administrative obstacles that workers encounter when dealing with government institutions or

public organizations. Cumbersome administrative processes and bureaucratic hurdles can slow down decision-making and hinder productivity in both public and private sectors. Several factors such as complex administrative processes, inefficient service delivery, corruption and bribery, overlapping responsibilities, and limited use of technology, contribute to the prevalence of bureaucracy and red tape in Nigeria. Unequal access to technology, including computers and software, can create disparities in productivity among workers, especially in sectors that rely heavily on digital tools (Zeb-Obipi, 2023).

- ***Inadequate Compensation / Lateness in Payment:*** Inadequate compensation is a situation where an employee's salary or remuneration does not adequately reflect the value of his or her work, skills, or contributions to the organization. It implies that the compensation provided is insufficient to meet the basic needs (food, shelter, clothing, education, healthcare) of employees,

or below what is considered fair or competitive in relation to industry standards, job responsibilities, and the employee's qualifications and experience; hence, it is inadequate to provide an acceptable standard of living and can lead to dissatisfaction, demotivation, and challenges in attracting and retaining talented individuals. In a research study conducted by the Society of Human Resource Management in 2012, 60% of employees expressed that compensation played a crucial role in their overall job satisfaction (Muguongo, Muguna & Muriithi, 2015). This places compensation just three percentage points below opportunities that leverage their skills and abilities, and only one percentage point below job security in the same year.

Lateness in payment is a situation where an employer fails to make timely payments to its employees as per agreed upon terms and schedules. It means that the payment is delayed beyond the expected or promised timeframe, which eventually causes financial hardships, inconvenience, and disruption at workplace. Salary delay can have serious consequences for employees who rely on their regular income to meet their daily expenses, take care of family demands, pay bills, and manage their financial obligations. It can as well result in financial hardship, stress, and anxiety, especially when the delay is unexpected or prolonged. Salary delay can also affect employee morale and productivity, as employees may feel undervalued and demotivated. According to Mohammed and El-Jajah (2019), money is believed to have a great tendency of bringing out a higher performance in workers when they are well-paid. It has been recognized as a chief source of satisfying workers' needs as well as social needs. It is the prime motivator in every work environment; and satisfies the psychological, security, and social needs of workers. Therefore, when workers receive their pay in due time and in commensurate with their effort, they are encouraged to put in more effort and contribute towards achieving organizational goals (Kpurunee & Nwibaedee, 2023). The definite amount of workers' salary is reliant on many reasons such as workers' experience on the job, their abilities and skill set, their prospects for improvement, and market rates. On the contrary, when their salary is delayed and not paid in commensurate with their effort, they lack the motivation to add value to the success of the organization. Yunus, et al., (2010) observed that a poor salary package can result in workers' dissatisfaction and low productivity; and public workers in Nigeria, experience poor salaries and more often, untimely pay for their monthly earnings. This has become typical to the point where it is now an accepted culture. Most public workers borrow from friends and family to supplement the absence or delayed salary. It continues from time to time and has a knock-on (cumulative) effect that reverberates throughout society. Debts are accumulated until they can be cleared, at times much later than planned or expected. This has a negative impact on workers' effectiveness and productivity

level. Poi, (2020) asserts that some workers augment their income from two or more different places to meet family demands and still do not get satisfaction. Therefore, Salary raise is needed in most government establishments to bring about a good work outcome. It can achieve workers' fulfillment as it comprises rewards that attract, motivate, and satisfy workers.

- **Lack of Training and Development:** According to Nassazi (2013), training and development is a function of human resource management that is used to fulfill the gap between current and expected performance. Training is an organized activity, planned and systematic to impart information and instructions to enhance the level of workers' skills, knowledge, and competency. It is the practice of coaching, mentoring, and inspiring workers by providing useful (appropriate) training, workshops, and seminars that motivate them to perform their tasks to the best of their ability and within standards set by the organization. Training plays a crucial role in preparing workers for their job function; and increasing their commitment level, as well as their skills and reciprocity (Zeb-Obipi & Kpurunee, 2021). The more prepared workers are, the more productive they are likely to be.

Lack of training and development is a situation where employees are not provided with sufficient opportunities to acquire knowledge, new skills, and competencies to enhance their work performance and career growth. Budget constraints, lack of resources in the organization, or a failure to recognize the importance of employee training and development are several factors that result in the lack of training and development. An untrained worker lacks the knowledge and prerequisite to handle expected duties. Their efforts are unproductive because it is not channelled in the right direction. However, an employee must thoroughly understand his job roles and everything the job entails; therefore, he needs 'role-specific instructions' and 'advanced domain-level training'. These training procedures educate workers on detailed domain knowledge of the fields they will be working in; their work processes; and the duties they are expected to perform. Malaolu and Ogbuabor (2013) investigated the effect of training and manpower development on workers' productivity and organizational performance using First Bank of Nigeria Plc. as a case study. Findings showed that training and manpower development significantly enhance employee proficiency and job productivity in the bank. Anggiani (2017) study revealed that skillful and knowledgeable employees are necessary for productivity. The more informed employees are, the more effective and efficient they will be.

- **Poor Employee Incentives:** Poor employee incentives are situations where the rewards and benefits received by the employee from the employer are inadequate, insufficient, and not aligned with employee needs and expectations. This can have negative impacts on organizational performance and productivity; and may lead to demotivation, lack of job satisfaction, and employee turnover. A study by the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) found that employees who are dissatisfied with their pay are more likely to look for employment opportunities elsewhere, and inadequate compensation is one of the key reasons for employee turnover. Incentives are crucial in motivating workers to productivity. It is used to promote outstanding performance, reinforce organizational values, and foster continuous learning by acknowledging desired behaviour and achievement (Milne, 2007). Incentives are given for the achievement of predetermined goals and are directly related to performance. It is an inducement given to encourage workers' effectiveness and motivation toward achieving greater performance. Tangible incentive systems (reward, pay, or benefits system) are strategic plans and programs for distributing financial rewards (Park & Sturman, 2016). It is regarded as a tool that influences workers' behaviour and enhances a

firm's effectiveness in meeting strategic objectives (Milne, 2007). More so, incentives stir up or provide zeal in workers for better performance. However, poor incentive discourages workers from carrying out their organizational tasks thereby, reducing the man-hour labour and productivity output. Rendering incentives is fundamental to the increase in the prerequisite for effective productivity. According to Koontz et al (1983), organizations must build into their entire system factors that will induce workers to contribute as effectively and efficiently as possible. Workers should be paid with consideration to their needs which include feeding, housing, clothing, and other higher needs. Therefore, to keep workers motivated and exert effort to achieve positive results, it is essential that their various needs are satisfied. Several studies have found that vastly incentive packages or programs are what stimulate workers' involvement and thus result in productivity (Becker & Huselid, 1999; Guthrie, 2001).

3. PROSPECTS (SOLUTIONS)

To increase employee productivity, Organizational leaders in Nigeria must stimulate and foster a culture that increases productivity, thereby providing the following:

➤ ***Salary Increase/welfare packs:*** Salary is an employee's fixed annual amount, paid monthly; and welfare packs are the all-encompassing or total package offered to employees over and above salary which increases their wealth and well-being (Armstrong & Taylor, 2023). Salary increments and welfare packs enable employees to meet financial obligations; maintain family expenses; and increase work productivity, therefore, salaries should maintain equity, and competitiveness, matching employee expectations and reinforcing positive employee behaviour (Poi, 2020). Employers are expected to carry out an upward review of workers' salaries and benefits, as these can attract talented workers, lead to a culture of performance and productivity, serve as a legal requirement, increase workers' satisfaction, and motivate them to work. Failure to do so can result in protest, legal action, financial penalties, and damage to the employer's reputation. Hence, employers must take proactive measures to enforce regular increments of employee salary/welfare packs; prioritize offering competitive compensation packages; and recognize and reward high-performing employees. Agusioma, Nyakwara & Mwiti (2019) submit that the lack of an effective reward system for compensating employees negatively impacts the level of employees' job satisfaction and work morale. Osterman (2010) asserts that workers' productivity is a function of workers' welfare, and Itodo & Abang (2018) opined that a good welfare package has a strong influence on employee performance level. Generally, in the Western world (US, Australia, & Canada), welfare packages are provided for workers. For instance, Canada in the 1970s, 1980s, and to date spent and is still spending proportionately more on employment benefits (Connell, et al., 1980) than most other countries in the world. They are mindful of the well-being of their workers as opposed to Nigeria.

➤ ***Proper Training and Development of Workers:*** Organizations must take steps to attract, motivate, and train their employees to execute the business strategy effectively and efficiently. Workers need to be allowed to grow and develop therefore, training programs need to be ingrained and instilled in the organizational culture, for success and productivity as training and development are a necessity for organizational success in a modern business environment. Training programs are crucial for performance and productivity as they prepare employees to use new knowledge, intellectual skills, and abilities to help achieve their organization's mission, vision, and values. It also assists workers and organizations in attaining diverse goals such as improving workers' morale, sense of fulfillment, and overall

competencies necessary to perform a job task. For instance, when workers are sent out for external training such as leadership development conferences or seminars, they are impacted positively as it boosts their intrapersonal and interpersonal skills; and they come back with such training to improve upon the organization by promoting better decision-making, building better teams in the organization and improving productivity which eventually manifests in the organization's return on investment (ROI); hence, training is a necessity and not a luxury. Western organizations are investing more than \$126 billion a year in workers' training and development (Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2017) so workers can positively impact organizational outcomes and contribute to economic and social development. According to Miller et al., (2014), the direct expenditure per worker on training and development increased from \$1,208 in 2014 to \$1,252 in 2016 (Ho et al., 2016). Consequently, there is a progressive investment in workers' training and development. This investment comprises diverse content areas that include managerial development, supervisory development, executive development, etc. Therefore, organizational leaders in Nigeria should use systematic approaches for assessing workers' performance; and provide suitable training and development opportunities, as well as effective worker performance assessment approaches.

➤ **Workplace Ethics:** Workplace ethics are principles and values that govern employees' behaviour, actions, and decisions in the workplace. It entails acting by organizations' standards of conduct; and involves a commitment to act with honesty, integrity, and fairness, and to uphold ethical consideration or standards in every aspect of work. Pinnington, Macklin, and Campbell, (2007) submit that ethics in the workplace is the moral evaluation of goals, policies, practices, and decisions taken in the organization as they impact human well-being, fairness, and decency. It encompasses a wide range of issues that include respect for diversity and inclusion; honesty and transparency in communication; avoidance of conflicts of interest; compliance with laws and regulations; and protection of confidentiality and privacy (Trevino & Nelson, 2021). According to Matthews (2014), ethics are the foundation of a good business; and organizations are established when individuals with different backgrounds and diverse interests unite on a common platform and work together toward achieving predefined goals and objectives. A set of principles is what guides the organization in its policies, decisions, and programs; and ethical organizational culture consists of workers and leaders adhering to a code of ethics (Kelchner, 2019).

In a competitive business environment, professional behaviour is required for productivity and success; thus, every organization should try to build and maintain the foundation of ethics. These professional behaviours include adhering to the organization's code of conduct; earning respect and increasing credibility and trust; seeking and providing expert guidance; championing professional development; promoting fairness in all measures and refraining from using an official position for personal benefits or nitpicking as well as micromanaging subordinates. Matthews (2014) asserts that the best organizations begin with a solid ethical footing that comprises integrity, respect, passion, result-oriented, risk-taking, and persistence. Studies have shown that an ethical workplace can enhance the organization's reputation and brand; and foster trust and respect between employees and the organization, which can lead to increased employee morale, employee retention, and work productivity (Trevino & Nelson, 2021). Therefore, leaders of organizations ought to enforce their workers to adhere to policies and implement their values in the strategy, plans, and decisions made.

➤ **Rewards and Promotion of Employees as at when due:** Organizational leaders should ensure due promotion and rewards as these are motivating factors that inspire workers to contribute sufficiently to achieving set goals. Several organizations have gained immense progress by complying with their business strategy through well-balanced reward and

recognition programs for workers. According to Deeprouse (1994), workers' motivation can be enhanced by providing them with effective recognition, rewards, and promotion. Rewards and promotion of workers should be accomplished in a timely and effective manner and should be based on a critical evaluation of workers' performance. Shaout and Yousif (2014) proposed several evaluation methods which include a ranking method, graphic rating scale, critical incident method, narrative essay, management by objectives, behaviourally anchored rating scales, 360-degree, 720-degree, assessment center, etc. To achieve greater productivity, organizational leaders should ensure that workers' performance goals and objectives adhere to SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, and Time-bound). Asim (2013) asserts that organizations systematically evaluate performance based on production count, personnel data, and judgmental methods. Nassazi (2013) provided different approaches for assessing workers' performance. These include supervisory assessment, self-assessment, subordinate assessment, peer assessment, team assessment, and client or customer assessment (internal and external clients or customers). Workers are responsible for achieving positive results through effective feedback and rewards for knowledge, abilities, and skills put into action.

➤ ***Provide security in all measures:*** These measures include physical security, cybersecurity, social, environmental, political, and economic security. The provision of security in a nation entails various measures taken by the government and other organizational institutions to ensure the safety and protection of employees and other members of society, as well as the nation's assets and infrastructure. The primary duty of the Nigerian government is to protect and guarantee the security of lives, as enshrined in section 14 (2b) of the 1999 constitution. They should enforce military measures to protect the country from external threats such as invasion or Boko haram terrorism; enhance the law enforcement agencies (police, intelligence agencies, and other security agencies) as they are responsible for preventing and responding to criminal activities and terrorism to maintain law and order within the country; and as well provide adequate border control measures such as surveillance system, border patrols, and screening processes. These can help ensure security in the nation as security is essential for the social, political, and economic stability of a nation. It represents a stable income and prosperity of a nation. It guarantees the stability of workers' innovation, creativity, and productivity; and Stewart (2004) opined that security is associated with national development. Therefore, productivity emerges when legitimate institutions and governance are strengthened to provide security.

4. CONCLUSION

Employees are most valuable in every organization as they contribute to the overall social and economic development of the nation. Hence, it is important to address several issues that include insecurity, negative working environment, inadequate compensation, poor employee incentives, excessive formalities and rigid procedures in public offices, that contribute to suboptimal productivity levels. Initiatives aimed at fostering a conducive work environment can play a pivotal role in unleashing the untapped potential of the workforce. Therefore, this study concluded that training and development, security (life and property insurance), salary increase, welfare packs, ethics in the workplace, worker incentives and promotion, etc. are crucial for the effective and efficient productivity of employees. Hence, organizational leaders in Nigeria should stimulate and foster a culture that increases employee productivity. Nigerian government should take responsibility for providing security of lives and properties as enshrined in Section 14 (2b) of the 1999 constitution.

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